

LEARNING GRAMMAR IN TEACHING FRENCH.

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Annotation: The article examines the place and significance of the grammatical aspect in teaching French to linguistic students from the point of view of traditional, communicative and functional approaches. Complexity is emphasized and the versatility of grammatical skills, among which are receptive (active and passive), as well as linguistic and speech grammatical skills, stipulating the need for an integrated approach in the formation of grammatical competence of future translators, which takes place in three stages.

Key words: grammatical competence, communicative method, functional approach, linguistic students.

The formation of grammatical competence of linguist students is an urgent problem, since only mastery of grammatical language at a high level component of communicative competence will provide graduates with the opportunity successfully solving problems in professional activities in conditions of increasing competition in the labor market.

Grammar occupies a special place in the system of linguistic sciences. Taking its name from the Greek word "gram" ("letter"), what makes it similar to the words "literate", "literate", grammar as an independent science has existed for more than two thousand years. Analysis of definitions of the word "grammar", presented in modern explanatory dictionaries, allows you to highlight its main meanings: 1) grammatical structure of the language; 2) a branch of linguistics that studies such system; 3) a set of change rules words, their connections into combinations, sentences, texts; 4) a textbook containing a description of the rules. At the same time, as the French note researchers (Henri Besse, Rémy Porquier), the term "grammar" remains ambiguous. Grammar includes description rules for the functioning of language in general; a set of regulations "imposed" to someone who already speaks the language; as well as a system of rules that will be learned by those who starts learning the language [8]. Others (Claude Germain and Hubert Séguin) distinguish linguistic grammar, which "describes grammatical competence without reference to practice"; special grammar (grammar of a specific language); pedagogical grammar. The latter offers "a description of specific manifestations of the language user's grammatical competence, perceived students. It is presented in the form of a grammar study program for a teacher or a grammar textbook for a student of a foreign language" [6]. J.-J. Richer calls pedagogical grammar "prescriptive or normative" [7]. The ambiguity of definitions emphasizes the complex and complex nature of grammar as a science and difficulties in choosing an adequate methodology for teaching it in the process of learning foreign languages.

The role of grammar in the methodology of teaching French as a foreign language changed under the influence of a number of factors, among which the most significant were the development of the theory of linguistics, changes in state policy in the field of education,

and learning outcomes. In determining the role of grammar. In teaching, it is necessary to note the presence of two opposing trends: on the one hand, an exaggeration of its role grammar and, on the other hand, reduction of hours, allocated for its study. Historical experience has shown that the implementation of any of extremes have a negative impact on learning results. To understand the role of grammar in teaching a foreign language, let's consider methods of its study within the framework of various approaches.

In the traditional approach, grammar was central and the goal of learning. Knowledge of grammar was identical to knowledge of the language, which was perceived as a set of grammatical rules. With a direct approach, grammar loses its status as the basis of language knowledge. Learning is implicit. The audiovisual approach considers grammar as a set of structures selected for development based on comparative analysis of native and foreign languages. Grammatical metalanguage is excluded. The communicative approach has become widespread in France since 1970 in connection with the promotion of a new learning goal - mastery of language as a means of communication.

Grammar is also studied in a communication situation; its development requires a careful selection of speech topics, intentions, which should reflect practical interests and the needs of students. The basis of communicative grammar are the ideas of communicative linguistics, psychological theory of activity, the concept of individuality development in the dialogue of cultures. The main position of communicative linguistics is the identification as a unit of speech communication an act regulated by the rules of speech behavior. The totality of speech acts form a coherent text - discourse. Basis for discourse formation is speech the communicant's intention, which implies a functional approach to the selection of material, mastery of communication tactics, mastery of the social roles of participants. The psychological basis was the personal activity approach, in which the individual is considered as a subject of activity, and training is aimed at developing speech skills. Training content the culture of its carriers also becomes, with training should take into account age and individual psychological characteristics of students' personality.

In the 80s of the 20th century, communicative approach to learning has entered a new stage. Categories such as communicative competence, linguistic personality, and linguistic consciousness have appeared. Methodological basis for linguistics becomes functionalism. The central position of the functional linguistics is the idea of language as a tool that allows a person cognize and describe the world around us. French scientists created in 1976 International Society of Functional linguistics. A book edited by A. Martinet "Functional grammar French language" [5]. Traditionally, grammar is characterized by the direction of study from the form to semantics. Functional grammar assumes the determining role of the approach "from semantics to the means of its expression."

Functional grammar is aimed at studying and describing the system of functions of grammatical means, which involves the implementation of two processes:

- 1) classification of grammatical means, participating in the implementation of the phenomena being studied;
- 2) analysis and generalization of semantic functions implemented in grammatical means.

The direction from functions to means corresponds to the point of view of the speaker, and the direction from means to functions corresponds to the point listener's view. This provides a synthesis of aspects of the grammar for the listener

(passive) and for the speaker (active). We stick to the following point point of view: grammar contains functional and formal aspects; they exist in organic unity. Formal represented by a system of grammatical units, classes and categories - that is, a nomenclature of means that are at the disposal of speakers and allow them to construct statements. The second aspect is the system patterns of functioning of grammatical units involved in expressing the meaning of a statement. Without formal grammar descriptions are impossible to study functional grammar. Teaching normative grammar French language for students of the Faculty of Philology of Orenburg State University revealed a number of questions regarding learning difficulties grammars:

- 1) students do not speak at the proper level knowledge of Russian grammar, which makes it difficult to understand similar structures language being studied and requires a lot of time to explain basic concepts;
- 2) many students have difficulty learning French grammar in French;
- 3) students carry out mechanical transfer of the forms and structures of the Russian language known to them to the phenomena being studied in the French language;
- 4) students do not have sufficiently developed skills in the correct use of forms of grammatical phenomena;
- 5) students use only simple ones grammatical structures;
- 6) students have difficulties when independently analyzing grammatical structures, conducting independent extracurricular work and self-control;
- 7) students have difficulty in situational use of grammatical phenomena;
- 8) grammar textbooks do not touch upon the nuances of the stylistic use of grammatical phenomena; exercises are aimed at developing language skills.

Teaching grammar to students must proceed from these realities, it is necessary to help them overcome the above difficulties. Modernization of the content of the grammatical aspect becomes relevant foreign language and the choice of forms and methods of studying it.

We share the opinion of those methodologists who believe that there is no universal method for developing grammatical competence. The choice depends on many factors: goals and conditions of training; categories of students, their level of training and learning ability; stage of training; character material being studied, etc.

Grammatical competence is a complex phenomenon, since grammatical skill is heterogeneous in nature. In its most general form it represents is the ability to retrieve grammatical means of speech from long-term memory. E.I. Passov defines it as the ability student to choose a model that is adequate speech task, and formulate it according to the norms of the language being studied [3].

Among grammatical skills there are receptive (active and passive), and language and speech grammar skills.

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